

EVALUATING AND ANALYZING TEACHING QUALITY

Elov Olimdjon Kamilovich

Navoi State University, " Geography and Basics
of Economic Knowledge." Lecturer

Niyatova Iroda Maxammatovna

Navoi State University, 3rd-year student at "School Management."

E-mail: mr.olimdjon@gmail.com

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Abstract. The article addresses the issue of evaluating and analyzing the quality of teaching. Assessing and analyzing teaching quality is considered one of the main priorities of the modern education system. Ensuring quality and effectiveness in education, objectively assessing each student's knowledge level, and identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the educational process to improve it are crucial. This article analyzes methods for evaluating teaching quality, methodologies for determining quality indicators, and various approaches in the assessment process, along with their advantages and disadvantages. Additionally, special attention is given to the importance of using modern innovative technologies to enhance teaching quality. The purpose of the article is to recommend effective mechanisms aimed at improving teaching quality.

Keywords: teaching quality, analysis, curriculum, effectiveness, knowledge, competence, skills, motivation, social competencies.

Introduction. In the education system, the quality of teaching is determined by the students' performance, the knowledge, and skills they acquire. Teaching quality not only influences students' academic knowledge but also affects their social, psychological development, and future professional activities. By evaluating and analyzing the quality of teaching, it becomes possible to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the educational process and further improve it.

In today's era of globalization, new demands and challenges are emerging for the education system. Due to economic and technological advancements, there is an increasing need to enhance the quality of human resources. Thus, assessing and continuously monitoring the quality of teaching in educational institutions has become particularly significant. Teaching quality plays a crucial role not only in improving the efficiency of the learning process but also in ensuring the holistic development of the younger generation.

This article explores the relevance of assessing teaching quality, the methodologies used for evaluation, and various approaches within the

educational process, along with their strengths and weaknesses. Improving the assessment process is considered one of the key steps towards enhancing educational quality.

What is Teaching Quality? Teaching quality refers to the set of factors that determine the effectiveness of the educational system, evaluated based on several criteria. These criteria include students' outcomes in the learning process, the content of educational programs, the qualifications of teachers, the learning environment, educational tools, and the needs of society.

The main factors influencing teaching quality are as follows:

Curriculum: The knowledge and skills imparted to students must align with modern standards.

Teacher Qualifications: The teaching methods, proficiency in using information technologies, and subject matter expertise of teachers play a crucial role in enhancing students' knowledge.

Learning Environment: Classrooms, laboratories, information resource centers, and other educational infrastructure are essential for quality learning.

Student Motivation and Engagement: Students' attitudes toward the learning process and their level of motivation significantly impact teaching quality.

The Importance of Evaluating Teaching Quality in Higher Education.

Today, assessing the quality of education in the higher education system is highly relevant and remains a key area of focus for scholars worldwide. Notable research by Russian scholars such as M.P. Afanasyev, I.K. Keyman, A.I. Sevruk, A.I. Subetto, V.A. Selezneva, Yu.P. Adler, V. Kachalov, A.M. Novikov, D.A. Novikov, T.V. Terenteva, and M.N. Kulakova, as well as Western scholars like P. Jacobson, L. Harvey, D. Timmerman, E.V. Balatskiy, J. Bolton, and F. Bukstein, contributes significantly to the understanding of teaching quality assessment. These studies often complement one another, offering a comprehensive perspective on how to evaluate educational quality.

The Concept of "Educational Quality". Before delving further, it's important to clarify the concept of "quality" in the context of teaching:

For **teachers**, quality is characterized by the availability of effective curricula, instructional materials, supporting resources, and favorable working conditions.

Students often perceive educational quality in terms of the learning environment within their institution and the "comfort" level of this environment.

Parents of students assess quality based on their children's individual development, academic progress, and success in both educational and practical activities.

Employers evaluate the quality of education by considering the active lifestyle of graduates, their knowledge, and skills, and their ability to make optimal decisions in real-world situations.

To better illustrate the diversity of perspectives on educational quality, a table is provided below, outlining the various types and distinctive characteristics associated with educational quality (Note: the table would typically follow here with specific details).

Figure 1

Types of Education Quality and Their Unique Characteristics

According to K.P. Mokhan, teaching in higher education embodies the following characteristics: teaching is the activity of delivering lessons to students, education involves the transmission of knowledge to learners, and teaching encompasses the process of instructing students in specific skills or concepts. The processes of teaching and knowledge transfer are essential components of the educational process.

However, if teaching does not lead to learning, it cannot be considered true education. In this sense, if the quality of education is not maintained, it

inevitably results in failure. This highlights that effective education is not merely about delivering information but ensuring that students internalize and apply what they learn.

Criteria for Evaluating Teaching Quality. Various criteria are used to evaluate the quality of teaching. The key factors that should be considered in the teaching process include:

"Level of Knowledge": This refers to students' understanding of a subject, including their theoretical knowledge and practical skills. These indicators are typically assessed through tests and examinations.

"Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills": The ability of students to think critically and approach problem-solving is a crucial requirement today. These skills prepare students to work independently and effectively in various situations.

"Social Competencies of Students": This includes the ability to work in teams, a sense of responsibility, interpersonal communication, and collaboration. Social competencies are essential for students to function effectively in team projects and diverse social contexts.

"Market Demands": This criterion assesses whether graduates are in demand in the labor market and their professional competitiveness. It is essential to consider how the knowledge and skills acquired during education can be applied in the workplace. This metric reflects graduates' employability and their professional competencies.

Each of these criteria not only measures the current state of students' abilities but also helps improve the educational process to better prepare students for real-world challenges.

The main indicators in the education quality assessment system and their content can be summarized as follows:

Table 2
Key Indicators of the Education Quality Assessment System

Criteria	Indicators
Students' Achievements in Teaching Levels	Through final assessment grades, the level of students' growth in knowledge and skills is determined.

Stability and Growth of Educational Quality	Final assessment grades evaluate the continuity and positive changes in educational quality.
Participation in International Knowledge Assessment Competitions	The number of students participating in international tests such as IELTS and CEFR, along with their results, allows for the assessment of their knowledge level based on international standards.
Students' Creative Activity	Participation in various creative competitions and the number of awards help to assess students' creative thinking and abilities.
Extracurricular Activities	Information on participation in clubs and other activities allows for the assessment of students' social engagement and activity level.

These indicators are crucial for further improving the quality of education and conducting effective analyses.

Methods for Evaluating Teaching Quality. To assess the factors influencing teaching quality, the following key methods are used:

Tests and Examinations. Tests and exams are fundamental tools for evaluating students' knowledge levels. They help determine the effectiveness of the teaching process by assessing students' understanding of individual subjects and their ability to apply knowledge practically.

Surveys and Interviews. Gathering feedback from participants in the educational process—such as students, teachers, parents, and employers—is essential. Surveys and interviews help gauge student satisfaction, the learning environment, and overall educational experiences. This method provides insights for improving the teaching process and making informed decisions.

Labor Market Analysis. The employability of graduates and their effectiveness in the workplace serve as indicators of teaching quality. This involves examining how well graduates' skills and knowledge align with labor market demands and how these competencies are utilized in real job settings.

Pedagogical Analysis. Pedagogical analysis involves evaluating teachers' methodologies and identifying their strengths and weaknesses in the educational process. It also assesses teachers' efforts in professional development and the integration of new teaching methods, which directly impacts teaching quality.

Methods for Improving Teaching Quality. Implementing modern approaches and technologies is crucial for enhancing the quality of education. Some of these methods include:

Use of Information Technologies. Leveraging information and communication technologies (ICT) is one of the new directions in education. It enables the organization of the learning process using digital and innovative approaches. Online platforms, distance learning, and interactive lessons simplify and enhance students' learning experiences.

Personalized Learning. By taking into account each student's individual needs, personalized learning plans can be developed. This approach improves the learning process by considering students' knowledge levels and unique learning characteristics.

Project-Based Learning. Project-based learning is effective for allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts. It enables students to develop their skills by solving real-world problems, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Integrated Education Programs. Integrating subjects allows for the delivery of comprehensive knowledge and skills, aligning with modern educational requirements. This approach enables students to gain expertise across multiple fields simultaneously, providing them with broader opportunities.

These methods, when applied effectively, can significantly enhance the quality of education, making it more adaptive, relevant, and aligned with the needs of students and society.

Conclusion. Implementing modern approaches and technologies in the process of improving teaching quality makes education more effective and engaging for students. The use of information technologies, personalized learning, project-based learning, and integrated educational programs plays a crucial role in enhancing students' knowledge and skills. These methods are effective tools for improving the quality of the educational process and preparing students for the modern labor market.

The quality of teaching in the education system is vital for students' future success, their active integration into society, and their competitiveness in the job market. Understanding the factors influencing teaching quality and employing various evaluation methods serve to ensure students receive the highest level of education possible. By rethinking modern educational practices, leveraging information technologies, and adopting an individualized

approach for each student, it is possible to achieve substantial improvements in teaching quality.

Focusing on enhancing the performance of both students and teachers, meeting employers' needs, and organizing the educational process at a high standard requires attention to teaching quality. This, in turn, lays the foundation for students' success in their professional careers.

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